

ENCAPSULATION OF MULTIWALL CARBON NANOTUBE VIA SELF-POLYMERIZED POLYDOPAMINE: THE IMPROVEMENT ON PROPERTIES OF ELASTOMERIC POLYURETHANE NANOCOMPOSITES WITH ULTRALOW NANOTUBE LOADINGS

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a facile and environmentally friendly surface modification method employing polydopamine (PDA) as a surface treatment agent for CNTs was used. It was found that the interfacial PDA layers did not only facilitate the dispersion of CNTs, but also strengthen the stress transfer from the polymer matrix to the CNTs, leading to greatly improved mechanical properties. The modification of CNTs was confirmed by FT-IR spectra and the surface morphologies of pristine CNTs and PDA-CNTs were observed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM), indicating that the surface of CNTs were uniformly coated by PDA.

The influences of PDA-CNTs on mechanical properties of polyurethane (PU)/PDA-CNTs nanocomposites were examined by tensile test. We found that with only 0.1 wt% loading, the Young's modulus and tensile strength of PU/PDA-CNTs 0.1 were increased by 10% and 64%, respectively, while the elongation at break was up to 81% increment. The enhanced mechanism of PDA-CNTs was studied and discussed by comparing with the pristine CNTs reinforced PU nanocomposites. Furthermore, the thermal behaviour and thermal stability of PU/PDA-CNTs were also studied by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). It was found that a higher melting point of soft segments and enhanced thermal stability was obtained by incorporating PDA-CNTs into PU matrix.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since the carbon nanotubes (CNTs) were discovered by Iijima [1], they have received intensive attention, since CNTs have extremely high modulus, high stiffness, low electrical percolation and high thermal conductivity [2], resulting from their characteristic structure, i.e., high aspect ratio and sp²-sp² electron hybridization. In particular, one of the most attractive applications is the preparation of CNTs/polymer nanocomposites [3, 4]. Nonetheless, the enhancements of CNTs on nanocomposites properties usually do not match the prediction from the theories, which is well known because of the poor dispersion of CNTs in matrix [5].

To improve the dispersion of CNTs, multiple approaches have been developed last two decades. To date, one of the most effective strategies is introducing functional groups by partially destroying the surface structure of CNTs, such as, carboxylate group [6-8], amine group [9, 10] and other special functional groups (i.e., C=C, -NCO and so on). However, not only these complicated chemistries

involved in the functionalization of CNTs make scalable production of CNTs/polymer nanocomposites still far from reality, but the high corrosive and toxic chemicals used in the process of modification have to be disposed carefully and properly after use.

Recently, some attempts were made on improvement of the CNTs dispersion without sacrificing characteristic structure of CNTs through synthesizing special copolymers [11] or using surfactants [12, 13]. The proposed mechanism is the formation of micelles or entanglement by long copolymer chains, and further debundle the individual CNT. Even if this method is effective to isolate CNTs, there are still some limitations, such as high cost and complicated chemistry to synthesize polymer with special structures as well as the desorption of nonreactive surfactants, in which the latter one will weaken the interfacial strength between CNTs and polymer matrix.

Polydopamine, as a hormone and neurotransmitter in human brain and body, has been reported to facilitate the dispersion of CNTs in aqueous, which is attributed to introduction of the large amount of polar groups in PDA layers [14, 15]. The special core-shell structure formed by the oxidative polymerization of dopamine on CNTs, can impart the strong interfacial strength between CNTs and polydopamine layer, even the interaction is still physical interaction. The enhanced interfacial strength can be contributed to entire coverage of CNTs by polydopamine layer and strong π - π stacking interaction between aromatic dopamine and the graphitic frame work [16, 17] (i.e., sp^2 hybridized carbons).

In view of the characteristics of PDA modified CNTs (PDA-CNTs), we hypothesized that PDA-CNTs may develop high-performance functional polymer nanocomposites. It is worth noticing that HDI trimer based PU system was used in this study, which is widely used in industry, but seldom studied in literatures. In this work, we synthesized the PDA-CNTs and then incorporated the PDA-CNTs into PU *via* in-situ polymerization. The influences of CNTs incorporation on PU structure, mechanical property, thermal behaviour and thermal stability were systematically studied.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 MATERIALS

The multi-walled carbon nanotubes with an average diameter of 9.5 nm and length of 1.5 μm synthesized by chemical vapor deposition were supplied by Nanocyl S.A. HDI trimer (N3390, from Bayer Company), defoamer (BYK A535), anhydrous N, N-Dimethylformamide (Sigma-Aldrich), dibutyltin dilaurate (95%, Sigma-Aldrich), dopamine hydrochloride (99%, Regent Chemicals) and tris(hydroxymethyl)-aminomethane hydrochlorid (99%, Regent Chemicals) were used as received. Polyol (Capa 7203, from Perstorp Company) was dehydrated in vacuum oven at 110 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ overnight before using.

2.2 PREPARATION OF PDA-CNTS AND FABRICATION OF PU/PDA-CNTS NANOCOMPOSITES

The procedure of PDA-CNTs was followed by the description in the literature [18]. 200 mg CNTs was dispersed into DMF containing Tris-buffer solution (pH 8.5) in ultrasonic bath. After formation of a homogeneous suspension, 2 mg/ml dopamine was added into CNTs/DMF suspension and the mixture of dopamine and CNTs was mildly magnetically stirred for 6 h at room temperature. The PDA-CNTs were obtained by repeating centrifugation and washed by deionized water for 3-4 times, to remove unreacted dopamine monomers and free polydopamine. In order to avoid the reagglomeration, the modified CNTs were dried by freeze dryer.

PU/PDA-CNTs nanocomposites were fabricated *via* in-situ polymerization. PDA-CNTs were firstly ultrasonically dispersed into DMF at the concentration of 0.3 mg/ml at least 1 h, followed by the addition of stoichiometric amount of polyisocyanate. Then, the obtained mixture was continuously stirred at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 h in nitrogen atmosphere. The viscous mixture of polyisocyanate and PDA-CNTs was concentrated by rotary evaporation. Finally, the nanocomposites were obtained by reacting with polyol and casting the solution onto the glass plate. Subsequently, the films were transferred to vacuum oven to remove the solvent. In this paper, the designation of the samples was defined as

PU/PDA-CNTs X. For example, PU/PDA-CNTs 0.1 means PU/PDA-CNTs nanocomposite, in which the weight percentage of PDA-CNTs was 0.1 wt%.

2.3 CHARACTERIZATION

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) was used to confirm the modification of CNTs by PDA layers and also monitor the reaction of isocyanate groups and hydroxyl groups. FT-IR was performed at average 32 scans between 650 and 4000 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} .

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was used to investigate the morphological structure of pristine CNTs and PDA-CNTs. The TEM images were obtained from a JEOL 2010 TEM at 200 kV. The fracture surfaces of nanocomposites were investigated by using a field emission-scanning electron microscope (Jeol FESEM 7600F) at 5 kV.

Mechanical properties of the nanocomposites were examined by tensile test. The testing procedure was followed by ASTM D638-V standard. The crosshead speed was kept at 20 mm/min. Tensile properties of samples with different formulations were tested at least five samples in order to obtain an average.

The thermal behavior of PU/CNTs nanocomposites was investigated using differential scanning calorimeter (DSC, Q10, Thermal Analyst Co., TA instruments, USA). The heating rate at the temperature range of -80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 220 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ was 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ in a nitrogen atmosphere at 50 ml/min.

The thermal stability was tested by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, Q500), from room temperature to 600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the heating rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ under air gas flow. The weight of the samples was kept around 10mg.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 MODIFICATION OF CNTS BY PDA LAYERS

The evidence of polydopamine coating onto the surface of pristine CNTs was confirmed by FT-IR spectra of pristine CNTs and PDA-CNTs, as shown in Figure 1. After the modification, some new peaks appeared. The strong absorption band at 3424 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the overlap of -OH groups stretching vibration and -NH [19], in which the -OH group could be assumed to be the moisture effect or slight oxidation of CNTs manufactured. Additionally, the characteristic peaks at 1739, 1540 and 1378 cm^{-1} are assigned to -C=O, -C=N and -C-N-C-, respectively [20]. The presence of these new peaks confirms that PDA was successfully coated onto CNTs.

The morphology of CNTs before and after modification was investigated by TEM, shown in Figure 2. The surface of pristine CNTs is smooth, as shown in Figure 2a). In contrast, the PDA-CNTs showed some roughness on the surfaces, caused by the coating of PDA layers (Figure 2b). Moreover, the TEM picture also indicates that the PDA layer was uniformly coated on the CNTs surface.

Figure 1: FT-IR spectra of pristine CNTs and PDA-CNTs

Figure 2: TEM images of (a) pristine CNTs and (b) PDA-CNTs.

3.2 FT-IR SPECTRA OF PU/CNTS NANOCOMPOSITES

Figure 3 shows the FT-IR spectra of neat PU, PU/Pristine CNTs 0.1 and PU/PDA-CNTs 0.1 nanocomposites in the range of 650-4000 cm^{-1} . The peak of free -NCO ($\sim 2270 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) disappeared and the peaks of urethane groups (~ 1700 , 1730 and 1680 cm^{-1}) appeared, which indicate the completion of reaction between -NCO and -OH [21]. However, no obvious differences can be observed from Figure 3 possibly due to the low CNTs loading in PU matrix.

Figure 3: FT-IR spectra of PU/CNTs nanocomposites

3.3 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF PU/CNTS NANOCOMPOSITES

After the modification of CNTs, the modified CNTs and pristine CNTs were incorporated into polymer matrix, in order to study the influences of CNTs addition on nanocomposites. The mechanical properties of PU/CNTs nanocomposites were evaluated by tensile test. The mechanical properties are shown in Figure 4. It was found that the tensile strength and modulus were increased by 10% and 64% by incorporating with only 0.1 wt% of PDA-CNTs. Moreover, the elongation at break was increased by 80%. This significant improvement on mechanical properties of PU/PDA-CNTs 0.1 was due to the existent of large amounts of reactive groups in PDA layer (i.e., -OH, -NH₂ and -NH-), which can react with -NCO groups. The presence of PDA layers not only facilitates the dispersion of CNTs in polymer matrix, but enhances the interfacial strength between CNTs and polymer matrix. The combination of these factors is responsible for the unusual increased mechanical properties.

While the decreases of tensile strength and modulus were observed with the incorporation of pristine CNTs. The decreased modulus can be attributed to interference of reaction between -NCO and -OH by pristine CNTs. Due to the special structure, the pristine CNTs exhibit strong adsorption ability, resulting in the strong interaction with the -NCO or -OH, further disrupting the stoichiometry of the

nanocomposites. The detailed mechanical properties of PU/CNTs nanocomposites were summarized in Table 1.

Figure 4: Mechanical properties of PU/CNTs nanocomposites

Table 1: Summary of mechanical properties of PU/CNTs nanocomposites

	Neat PU	PU/PDA-CNTs 0.1	PU/Pristine CNTs 0.1
Young's modulus/MPa	0.9±0.2	1.0±0.1	0.4±0.1
Tensile strength/MPa	1.1±0.1	1.8±0.2	0.7±0.1
Elongation at break/%	245±32	444±54	636±29

3.4 THERMAL BEHAVIOUR AND THERMAL STABILITY OF PU/CNTS NANOCOMPOSITES

The influences of CNTs on the thermal behaviors and thermal stability of as-prepared PU nanocomposites were investigated by DSC and TGA techniques, respectively. The DSC results are shown in Figure 5, and the thermal data are listed in Table 2. It was found that neat PU and PU/PDA-CNTs 0.1 nanocomposites showed nearly same glass transition temperatures (T_g). While the increased melting temperatures associated to soft segments (T_{mSS}) can be obtained by incorporating PDA-CNTs into polymer matrix. Noticeably, T_g , T_{mHS} and T_{mSS} of PU/Pristine CNTs 0.1 nanocomposite were decreased significantly compared to neat PU and PU/PDA-CNTs, which further elucidates that the addition of pristine CNTs interfered the reaction between -NCO and -OH.

The thermal stabilities of all the nanocomposites were evaluated by TGA in air atmosphere, as shown in Figure 6. As can be seen from Figure 6, the thermal stability of neat PU, PU/Pristine CNTs and PU/PDA-CNTs 0.1 does not show any difference below 300 °C. However, at higher temperature the CNTs modified nanocomposite exhibit higher stability, which is attributed to high thermal stability of CNTs. Furthermore, the PU/Pristine CNTs 0.1 shows less stability compared to PU/PDA-CNTs 0.1 (inset in Figure 6). This once again confirmed that the reaction between -NCO and -OH was disturbed by pristine CNTs.

Figure 5: DSC curves of PU/CNTs nanocomposites

Table 2: DSC results of PU/CNTs nanocomposites

	Neat PU	PU/PDA-CNTs 0.1	PU/Pristine CNTs 0.1
$T_g / ^\circ\text{C}$	-52	-52	-54
$T_{mSS} / ^\circ\text{C}$	34	45	11
$T_{mHS} / ^\circ\text{C}$	153	152	136

Figure 6: TGA curves of PU/CNTs nanocomposites

4. CONCLUSION

The pristine CNTs were modified by PDA layers *via* self-polymerization and the modified CNTs were successfully incorporated into polyurethane matrix. It was found that mechanical properties of PU/PDA-CNTs nanocomposites were obviously increased by incorporating only 0.1 wt%. This unusual improvement is attributed to the excellent dispersion of PDA-CNTs and the enhanced interfacial strength, which are responsible for the improved stress transferring ability of load from polymer matrix to fillers. The incorporation of PDA-CNTs increased the crosslinking of nanocomposites, which was confirmed by the increased melting point of soft segments. Moreover, the thermal stability of PU/CNTs nanocomposites was also improved by the CNTs addition.

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